

Painting the invisible Cosmic structures with radio galaxies

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Motivation

- The ambient medium of jetted radio galaxies can affect their morphology at both small and large spatial scales. Hence the radio morphology can be used to estimate the presence and properties of the ambient medium, e.g. the presence of filaments, bridges, and edges. My work aims to study the properties of various intergalactic and intracluster media through the use of radio galaxy morphologies.
- Similar studies have been conducted before, where the effects seen on the radio morphology were evident to environmental properties, e.g. Subrahmanyan et al. (2008), Safouris et al. (2009), Parekh et al. (2020), Brienza et al. (2023).

(a) Parekh et al. (2020)

(b) Brienza et al. (2023)

(c) Safouris et al. (2009)

(d) Subrahmanyan et al. (2008)

Figure 1: Examples of radio galaxy morphology being affected by asymmetry in the ambient medium.

Data

- I used deep radio continuum and spectral index images from the MeerKAT Galaxy Cluster Legacy Survey (MGCLS, Knowles et al 2022).
- Available redshift surveys overlapping with some of the MGCLS fields like 2dFGRS and LARCS were used to characterise the galaxy environment around radio sources.

Preliminary results

Figure 2: Galaxies showing signs of interaction with the ambient medium. All of these galaxies are in the foreground of the cluster at which the MGCLS image points.

- Galaxy 1 morphology suggests that there exist a radio/optical invisible structure that has disrupted the north lobe.
- Galaxy 2 and 3 morphologies suggests that they are experiencing significant ram pressure from ambient media which are not part of the background cluster.

Figure 3: Redshift and 3D distribution of galaxies in the direction of galaxies 1, 2, and 3.

Pressure estimates of the filamentary environment

Figure 4: IGM pressure estimates from radio galaxies overlaid with WHIM pressure estimates from X-ray observations (Malarecki et al., 2013).

- Backed up by the redshift and 3D distributions (Fig. 3), we believe that there exist **filament-like structures** aligning along the locations of all 3 galaxies.
- Morphology and positions of galaxy 2 and 3 suggests that they are infalling into the filament at $z = 0.113$ and $z = 0.126$, respectively.
- Their degree of bending is proportional to their surrounding medium ram pressure estimates.
- Galaxy 1, 2, and 3 were used to estimate their surrounding IGM pressures, which were then compared to literature WHIM pressure estimates from X-ray observations of galaxy filaments (Fig. 4).
- Their IGM pressure estimates lie very close to the WHIM pressure estimates from X-ray observations of galaxy filaments.

Takeaways

- Radio galaxies can act as kpc and Mpc scale probes of their environments and can provide estimates of ambient medium properties.
- They also allow us to trace WHIM, which is currently invisible at all wavelengths.
- Together with observations from other wavelengths (optical data in this case), they allow us to probe the properties of the large scale structure.

References

